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‘CHATVAARI DARSHANA’ OR THE FOUR FACTOR APPROACH OF MANAGING THE HUMAN RESOURCES

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Abstract: The prevalent management system is an external process of exerting control over the performance of others. It sets for a clear division of separation of management from the people in the organisation. What we need is an unconditional commitment of the people where the entire organisation unites together for facing the challenges. For this, an integral approach of human management focused on the soul, intellect, mind and body is recommended. Progress of a person relies on the progress of his four critical elements such as the body, soul, intellect and mind. The ‘Chatvaari Darshana’ which means the philosophy based on four factors advocates for addressing and managing the dynamics of the soul, body, intellect and mind of people in an organisation for sustainable development.

Keywords: Conditional Workplace, Indian Vedic Philosophy, Soul, Intelligence, Mind, Body.

Introduction

All definitions on management portray it as a process of planning, organising, directing and controlling all organisational activities. But an in-depth evaluation of the turbulent organisational atmosphere today, we can precisely gather the weaknesses of the current management perceptions in tackling the crucial organisational issues. The prevalent management system is an external process of exerting control over the performance of others. It views managers and people in an organisation as different entities in which one has to formulate policies, goals, issue directions for its accomplishment and other has to obey and perform as per the required standards. This dual class bifurcation of the organisation is the basic feature of the existing management system even though it envisages team work and organisational integrity. In other words, the system is unable to provide a constructive approach for the alleviation of organisational sectarianism. This sectional classification which is not a willfully incardinated aspect, unfortunately became the explicit feature of the present management system.

Organisational Dissension

The polarization in firms can no way contribute to a peaceful, creative and healthy work environment. It could not ensure or maintain peace and harmony in the organisation. A ‘**conditional workplace**’ is the net result of this bi polar mechanism. That means, survival of the organisation depends on the fulfillment of certain conditions of the workforce and the management. If any of these conditions fail, it will adversely affect its operations and may detach people. But in the case of an unconditional environment, a crisis can voluntarily unite together people associated with the organisation. The conditional commitment of people from both sections (Management and Employees) towards organisation must be transformed to an unconditional or natural commitment to establish real peace and harmony in the organisation. But it is rarely seen in business organisations. For this, the present mind set of the people must be thoroughly revived. We can observe unconditional or natural pattern of commitment in the family, social and some political organizations. But it is rarely seen in business organisations. This is due to the reason that in business organisations, people are viewed as resources or physical capital, employed for an optimum utilisation. Their performance and productivity are evaluated without giving much importance to their emotions and feelings.

Indian Vedic Philosophy and Human beings

As per Indian philosophy, an integral human being is a combination four elements; **(1) Soul, (2) Body, (3) Intellect and (4) Mind**. Upanishad “interprets that soul is the owner of the human body which is like a ‘chariot’, where intellect is the charioteer and mind is the bridle that controls the entire system. Progress of a person relies on the progress of his body, soul, intellect and mind. Usually, many are of the view that body is more important than other factors and considers physical comfort and luxury as reasons for happiness and satisfaction of human beings. But it is a fact that mental worry destroys all joy and happiness brought by physical comfort and luxury. Likewise, intellectual happiness also is a crucial element in this process. Even after a person gets comforts for the body and mentally joyful, if he is troubled with some intellectual problems, he is reduced to a state almost similar to madness. For instance, a lunatic may have all physical comforts, he may be perfectly healthy and properly cared for by his relatives; but he does not possess intellectual happiness.

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A person with a balanced mind and strong intellectual ability only can deeply concentrate in his work and enjoy the physical benefits. Here a four factorial approach is framed which is intended to provide a comprehensive perspective while managing people. This approach suggests for an in-depth analysis of the four elements which makes man i.e., Soul, Body, Intellect and Mind, instead of concentrating on a single point i.e., Body, or physical needs. These factors are integrated, inter-related and complimentary to each other. But for the purpose of executing a scrupulous management process, needs of these four must be identified and addressed in order to attain an exhaustive progress of the organisation as well as the individuals.

FF Approach in Human Management

The Four Factor Approach relies on a four-point programme for envisaging a scientific management of the people in an organisation. This is clearly portrayed in the model depicted above. This four-point programme of the people management process are 1) Manage Soul, 2) Manage Intelligence, 3) Manage Mind and 4) Manage Body. The model considers internal and external aspects (requirements) of people while managing them. It is to be noted that the prevalent system emphasis on external or physical needs of people. The modus operandi of this approach is detailed below;

1) Manage Soul

‘Knowing of self’ is the major notion behind this aspect. One who has precisely realised himself can easily walk over all intricacies in his life. He will be always well equipped with all sorts of qualities such as determination, self-control, bravery, commitment, dedication, hardworking attitude, patience, self-reliance etc. He can definitely acquire mastery over his senses and can influence and attract others. This is purely an internal process whereby one needs to learn and acquire skills for realising self. But it is the duty of the organisation to persuade its people in this self-knowing exercise. This will help them to realise about their actual caliber, skills, knowledge base, character deficiencies etc. It can also give answers to so many internal questions queried by one’s mind related with his personal and official life.

The self-knowing exercise will also lead to self-introspection which is a major advantage of this process. By doing this, one can effectively correct mistakes, improve efficiency, refine character and lead a remarkable life. Meditation (Mind concentration) is an important technique for realising self. Modern world has proved that, if followed scientifically, ‘yoga’ and ‘dhyana’ can reduce mental agony and stress. Now, in the medical science also, they are following an approach of integrating mind and body in the treatment process. So, meditation (dhyana) and yoga can provide valuable contributions in the self realising process. The success of this process highly depends on the effectiveness of the joint effort made by the people and the management.

2) Manage Intelligence

Power of the people for reasoning, learning and understanding must be enhanced by adopting suitable intelligent tests and education methods. By conducting intelligent tests, a person’s intelligence can be rated and the need for improvement can be inferred. This will help to decide the type of education needed by the people. It is not necessary that intelligence tests be in the form of written exams. Intelligence can be conducted by assigning special tasks to the people. Here their intelligence is rated by analysing their mode performance and quality of the results produced. The process of intelligence management is highly essential in knowing one’s intellectual capacity and its efficient utilisation for the progress of the organisation.

3) Manage Mind

It is aimed at reducing the mental strain or stress of people. We can identify many reasons of stress. But basically, these reasons can be categorized into official and personal. It is the major responsibility of the management to identify these reasons and take adequate steps for its elimination or reduction for a progressive functioning of the organisation. Aforesaid two categories causing are detailed below;

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a) **Official Stressors:** This category contains unfavourable conditions at the workplace which affects people while at work. Some of the major factors under this category are;

- i) Heavy Work load
- ii) Lack of adequate Rest
- iii) Inducting people to jobs in which they are not interested
- iv) Lack of adequate equipments or infrastructure at the workplace
- v) Outdated technology
- vi) Work monotony
- vii) Lack of systematic or proper communication
- viii) Unfavourable attitude of the superiors
- ix) Problems with co – workers
- x) Lack of adequate monetary benefits and other welfare facilities etc.

b) **Personal Stressors:** This category contains family matters, diseases and other problems faced by a person in his personal life. All these issues official as well as personal must be identified and resolved for building a balanced mind among the people. Providing physical comforts by not understanding or analysing the minds of people will not sustain the organisation for long. In order to gather the minds of the people sufficient forums or joint committees of management & people must be established for exchange of views, opinions complaints, requirements, suggestions etc. Organising family meetings, expert counselling, expert speeches etc. in a systematic manner can be a relief to people in resolving or reducing their personal problems.

4) Manage Body

Attention on this factor will be useful only if other three factors were properly managed. Physical comforts in no way can influence people if they are mentally worried. It is said that, “a modest meal served with dignity and affection tastes better than the best delicacies served with disrespect.” An organisation is structured by so many hierarchical divisions. These hierarchical divisions are intended for the proper distribution of responsibilities and duties of the organisation and not meant for discriminating people. In no way different departments, jobs, designations etc. create a feeling of discrimination among the minds of the people. These organisational parameters should act like different limbs of the same body.

There cannot be any conflict in the different parts of the same body. There is complete identity of interest and identity of belonging. This idea must be kept alive to avoid discrimination and sectarianism in the organisation. People in an organisation are different to one another on the basis of their economic, social, political and educational background. They may have different views, beliefs and interests. They may differ in their skills, jobs and designations. But they stood for achieving a ‘common organisational goal’. This aspect of common goal must be given supreme status and influence all people in the organisation for building up an unconditional work place. A people management mechanism based on four factors, i.e., soul, intellect, mind and body aspect only can guide the organisation in this process.

Conclusion

This approach views and treats people as human beings and considers all sections of people in the organisation on the basis of four factors influencing human beings; soul, intellect, mind and body. In other words, their existence depends on these four factors. How intensively a person realizes himself, how intensively he utilises his intelligence for achieving his goals, how intensively he concentrates his mind towards his goals and how intensively he engages his body for the desired goals, so intensive will be the success achieved by him.

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